

THE ILLUSTRATION OF FORM OF LETTER IN “SEA PRAYER” BY KHALED HOSSEINI AND ANALYSIS OF "SEA PRAYER"

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Annotation: The following article is about the short work “Sea Prayer” by Afghan-American writer Khaled Hosseini and analyze this form of letter in “Sea Prayer”. The usage words, styles, main ideas and illustrations are explored. The main topic is the form of letter from father to son and death a thousand of people in sea to find safe place. Also, the work based on Alan Kurdi who was 3-year-old child and his death. It is also a vivid portrait of their life in Homs, Syria.

Key words: pray, refugee, Taliban, style, Homs, epistolary, Sea Prayer, war, symbols.

Sea Prayer by bestselling author Khaled Hosseini and beautifully illustrated by Dan Williams. They introduce challenges and difficulties facing displaced persons from around the world, forced to leave their homes in dangerous or difficult circumstances. Sea Prayer is a love letter from a father to his son as they flee a deadly war zone and embark on a perilous sea journey in search of a new home. Inspired by the real-life story of Alan Kurdi, the three-year-old Syrian refugee who drowned on his journey to reach safety in Europe in 2015, it introduces the heart-wrenching challenges of the refugee experience and opens up important PSHE and Literacy Citizenship objectives in the classroom. Sea Prayer is a thought-provoking class reader for pupils aged 9–12 years. This Resource Pack is designed to help learners explore universal human values and mutual respect and understanding, exploring themes of love, separation and what it means to call somewhere ‘home’ – and building empathy towards refugees and asylum seekers. On a moonlit beach a father cradles his sleeping son as they wait for dawn to break and a boat to arrive. He speaks to his boy of the long summer of his childhood, recalling his grandfather’s house in Syria, the stirring olive trees in the breeze, the bleating of his grandmother’s goat, the clanking of the cooking pots. And he remembers, too, the bustling city of Homs with its crowded lanes, its mosque and grand souk, in the days before the sky spat bombs and they had to flee. When the sun rises they and those around them will gather their possessions and embark on a perilous sea journey in search of a new home . . .

A short, powerful, illustrated book written by beloved novelist Khaled Hosseini in response to the current refugee crisis, Sea Prayer is composed in the form of a

letter from a father to his son on the eve of their journey. Watching over his sleeping son, the father reflects on the unsafe sea-crossing that lies before them. It is also a vivid portrait of their life in Homs, Syria, before the war, and of that city's swift transformation from a home into a deadly war zone. Khaled Hosseini is the first Afghan-born American novelist writing in English. How to cite this paper: This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License. *Advances in Literary Study* He was born in 1965 in Kabul, Afghanistan, and moved to the United States with his family later and graduated from the University of California. His works include *The Kite Runner* (2003), *A Thousand Splendid Suns* (2007), and *The Mountains Echoed* (2013) and *Sea Prayer* (2018). More than 55 million copies have been sold worldwide. With personal and specific expression, he presents Afghanistan, a remote and mysterious country, to the wider world in a delicately literary style. The new work, entitled *Sea Prayer*, is a short, illustrated book which Hosseini wrote in response to the current refugee crisis and the haunting image of young Alan Kurdi, the three-year-old Syrian boy whose body washed up on the beach in Turkey in September 2015. Khaled Hosseini's new work *Sea Prayer* was published in 2018, which was also his first work writing for children. It is also a deeply moving and gorgeously illustrated short story for people of all ages. The theme, which he is good at, is about emotional ties between family members. Readers from foreign countries once commented that by reading this book, they can find the touching feeling again when reading *The Kite Runner* and *A Thousand Splendid Suns*.

Sea Prayer is exquisitely illustrated by Dan Williams, who is a very famous British illustrator. The first half of the watercolor illustrations in the book with terrestrial color expresses the warmth of hometown, while the second half conveys the dilemma brought by the war in a gray tone. The steel-blue sea symbolizes the unknown fear. The contrast between the illustrations before and after deepens the tension of the text to a higher degree. *Sea Prayer*, with its epistolary style, tells the story of a Syrian father who was sailing across the sea to Europe at night. The father watched his son who was sleeping soundly and told him about the beautiful scenery of his Syrian hometown in the past and the dangers of drifting on the sea. He spoke of the long summers during his childhood to his boy by recalling his grandfather's house in Syria, the stirring of olive trees in the breeze, the bleating of his grandmother's goat, the clanking of her cooking pots. *Sea Prayer* is an attempt to pay tribute to the millions of families, like Alan Kurdi's, who have been splintered and forced from home by war and persecution. Hosseini hopes to inspire people to look at the issue of

refugee from a perspective of humanitarianism by such work as the Sea Prayer. Currently, there are various comments on the Sea Prayer in a number of newspapers and magazines abroad.

The Guardian comments that “Dan Williams’s watercolors are a haunting companion to the contemplative and poetic story of a father fleeing Syria with his son. The Sunday Times Magazine comments that “The book may be brief, but it is beautiful, poetic—a distillation of his strengths. It combines Hosseini’s multiple personae, as a wordsmith, as a father and even as a doctor.” Publishers Weekly, STARRED BOX Review claims that “Hosseini’s story, aimed at readers of all ages, does not dwell on nightmarish fates; instead, its emotional power flows from the love of a father for his son. In Williams’s loosely stroked ink-and-wash spreads, the corals and greens of the Syrian countryside give way to war’s gray shadows and the sea’s blue hues. Expansive views of sky and water both temper the text’s emotional build and render the figures in them small and fragile. Together, the evocative illustrations and graceful, compelling prose make it clear that Marwan and his parents have no choice but to trust the sea.” Hosseini said that some countries from European Union (EU) are closing their doors to refugees, and showing a marked disinclination to refugee issue. The refugee issue is not only in connection with European countries, but also one that needs to be shared and faced by the whole world. EU must undertake the responsibility to alleviate conflicts between refugees and receiving countries, and move quickly turns some enlightened policies into reality, thereby subsiding the violent conflicts in some areas. It is very difficult to change the situation of refugees by literary works, but those kinds of stories must be told. Hosseini wrote this work Sea Prayer with a strong desire to inspire people to look at the refugee issue on humanitarian grounds. Numbers on the news may not resonate with us emotionally, but they are living people behind the headlines. Empathy for stories is an innate human instinct. If we want to understand something, we must learn how to care about it. If we want to care about something, we must have empathy firstly.

There are many symbols in this work. For instance, The farm symbolizes peace and nostalgia. The narrator grew up on a farm, living with his parents and brothers. The narrator has fond memories if this time as being peaceful and content. Unfortunately, such peace appears to be scarce or nonexistent in Syria following the outbreak of the Syrian Civil War. And, The city, Homs, symbolizes prosperity and peaceful coexistence, which are dynamics that can be disrupted by war, violence, and civil unrest. The narrator describes pre-war life in the city as characterized by vibrancy and tranquil coexistence among inhabitants.

However, not only is such peace destroyed by war, but the general infrastructure of the city is destroyed along with the well-being of its denizens.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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